

Supplementary Table 4 Other autoantibodies in anti-CCP2-positive and -negative RA and controls

Antigen	Antibody frequencies (%) ^a				Antibody levels (median)		
	CCP2+	CCP2-	controls	P-value ^b	CCP2+	CCP2-	P-value ^c
Ro60/SSA	4.8	5.3	1.6	0.61	419.0	712.8	0.003
Ro52/SSA	3.4	5.3	1.4	0.02	1252.8	1320.4	0.073
PMScl100	3.1	4.9	2.2	0.02	156.8	154.1	0.471
dsDNA	2.8	3.9	1.9	0.99	25.5	25.4	0.886
La/SSB	3.1	2.7	1.1	0.63	232.6	381.2	0.045
U1 RNP-C	2.1	3.6	1.6	0.02	107.2	147.2	0.008
Fibrillarin	3.1	1.8	1.6	0.04	29.0	33.2	0.838
CENPB	2.1	2.0	0.5	0.90	116.2	123.5	0.628
Jo1	2.3	1.5	1.4	0.18	92.1	126.2	0.597
Rip P2	1.6	2.5	1.9	0.08	111.8	76.8	0.05
U1 RNP-A	1.2	2.7	1.4	0.003	377.1	631.8	0.002
U1 RNP-70	2.0	0.7	2.4	0.005	67.9	71.2	0.578
RNA pol III	1.5	1.6	1.6	0.77	436.1	427.1	0.776
Scl70	1.5	1.3	0.8	0.74	197.7	194.4	0.439
SmD	1.4	1.0	1.9	0.43	404.0	413.0	0.762
PCNA	0.8	1.7	1.6	0.41	196.5	241.6	0.317
SmBB	0.5	1.0	1.6	0.13	223.6	185.2	0.221

^a Bold figures indicate significantly higher antibody frequencies than in controls. P-values show differences in ^b antibody frequencies and ^c antibody levels, between anti-CCP2-positive and anti-CCP2-negative RA.